

A review of the advantages and disadvantages The role of renewable energy in the Global future

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Abstract:

Global warming due to the greenhouse effect phenomenon and climate change are among the greatest environmental challenges of the present age that have attracted the attention of scientists in many fields.

Fossil fuels, meanwhile, burn large amounts of carbon dioxide into the atmosphere, which has a direct effect on global warming;

Increased consumption of fossil fuels is one of the main reasons for this phenomenon. In addition, global energy consumption has been accompanied by increasing demand, so that for the global energy outlook, it is predicted that under a typical scenario, taking into account the energy consumption of developed and developing countries, energy demand by 2030, 60% (Compared to 2019 - 60% of this growth in energy demand is in developing countries such as China and India).

This article discusses in detail the advantages and disadvantages of the role of renewable energy in the future of the world, and finally offers practical solutions to protect the planet from extinction.

Keywords: Renewable energy, fossil fuels, solar energy, geothermal, wind energy